

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids. Part VII. Preparation, Properties and Analytical Application of Thorium (IV) *N-m-Tolyl-m-Nitrobenzohydroxamate*

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Manuscript received 23 June 1976, revised 17 January 1977, accepted 10 February 1977

A new complex of thorium(IV) with *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* was prepared by reacting an aqueous solution of Th with an alcoholic solution of *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* at 60° and adjusting the pH 4-4.5. The infrared spectra and thermal analysis of the complex have been discussed. The use of *N-m-T-NBHA* for gravimetric determination of thorium is described.

IN continuation with previous work on the use of *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* (*N-m-T-NBHA*)^{1,10} a new solid complex Th *N-m-T-NBHA* is described. The infrared spectra, DTA and TGA of *N-m-T-NBHA* thorium complex were studied. The use of *N-m-T-NBHA* as a gravimetric reagent for micro-gram determination of thorium in presence of foreign ions has been reported.

Experimental

Chemical

All chemicals used were of G.R. and AnalaR grades of E. Merck and B.D.H. respectively unless otherwise stated.

Reagents

The *N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid* was synthesised by the method described earlier¹¹.

The aqueous stock solution of thorium was prepared by dissolving 1.3805 g. thorium nitrate in 250 ml. of double distilled water and the final concentration was determined volumetrically¹².

Procedure

In a lite beaker, 10 ml of a 0.001M solution of thorium nitrate and about 500 ml water were heated at 60° on a water bath. Then 20 ml of 0.1M solution of *N-m-T-NBHA* in ethanol was added dropwise with constant stirring followed by 0.1N ammonium hydroxide until complete precipitation was obtained. The pH 4-4.5 was adjusted by ammonium acetate and acetic acid solution. The granular precipitate

thus formed was digested for 2-3 hrs over a steam bath, filtered through a sintered glass crucible of porosity G4 and washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with 30 per cent aqueous ethanol (5×10 ml). The complex was purified by reprecipitation from a mixture of ethanol-water and dried at 110°.

The same procedure was used for gravimetric determination of thorium and the complex was weighed directly.

Analysis

Weighed quantity of complex was decomposed with a mixture of perchloric, sulphuric and nitric acids and the thorium content was determined volumetrically with EDTA using xynol orange as an indicator.

Thermal Analysis

Simultaneous plots of T.G. and DTA were obtained at a constant heating rate of 8°C/min on a Metler thermal analyser fitted with a 12 channel recorder. Al₂O₃ was used as a reference material for DTA.

Spectra

The infrared spectra of the reagent and thorium complex were recorded on Perkin Elmer Model 137 spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics as KBr pellets.

Results and Discussion

The physical properties of the complex are given in Table 1. The data on gravimetric determination of thorium(IV) in presence of various foreign ions are given in Table 2 and Table 3. The DTA and TGA curves of the complex are reproduced in figure 1.

N-m-tolyl-m-nitrobenzohydroxamic N-m-T-NBHA, I, is a very weak acid³ (pK_a 8.33 at 25°) and reacts

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE THORIUM-N-*m*-TOLYL-*m*-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEXES

Colour	: Yellowish			
m.p., °C	: 210*			
pH of precipitation	: 4-4.5			
Analysis %	C	H	N	Th
	Calculated	51.07	3.37	8.51
Found	51.10	3.35	8.50	17.65
DTA				
1st Exotherm	: 210°			
2nd Exotherm	: 600°			
Residue	: ThO ₂			
TGA				
Weight loss calculated:	79.93%			
Found	: 79.56%			

* The complex is decomposed.

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THORIUM WITH N-*m*-TOLYL-*m*-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID

Th Taken mg	Th Found mg	Error
5.00	5.01	+0.01
5.00	5.00	±0.00
7.50	7.48	-0.02
10.00	9.98	-0.02
15.00	15.02	+0.02
15.00	15.01	+0.01

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF THORIUM FROM OTHER METALS

Thorium Taken mg	Foreign Ions mg	Masking agent	Thorium Found mg
5.00	Ag ⁺ 60	Acetate	5.00
5.00	Be ²⁺ 80	Acetate	5.03
5.00	Pb ²⁺ 80	Acetate	5.01
5.00	Mn ²⁺ 80	Acetate	4.98
10.00	Ni ²⁺ 80	Acetate + Citrate	9.98
10.00	Cu ²⁺ 80	Cynide + Acetate	9.97
10.00	Zn ²⁺ 80	Acetate + Cyanide	10.02
5.00	Cd ²⁺ 80	EDTA	5.00
5.00	Hg ²⁺ 70	Acetate + Citrate	5.03
5.00	Pd ²⁺ 100	Citrate + Oxalate	4.98
5.00	Ga ³⁺ 100	Acetate + Citrate	5.02
5.00	Al ³⁺ 100	Acetate + Citrate	4.97
5.00	Bi ³⁺ 70	Acetate + Tartrate	4.97
5.00	Sb ³⁺ 80	Acetate + Tartrate	5.01
5.00	La ³⁺ 80	Acetate + Citrate	4.98
5.00	Ti ⁴⁺ 100	Acetate + Tartrate	5.00
5.00	Zr ⁴⁺ 100	Citrate + Oxalate	5.02
5.00	V ⁵⁺ 100	Acetate Mg-EDTA	5.02
5.00	Mg ²⁺ 80	Acetate + Citrate	5.01
5.00	U ⁶⁺ 60	Acetate + Tartrate	5.02

to around 150°-180° indicating the absence of water molecule. DTA for the complex shows two exotherms, first at 225°, a very sharp one along with loss in weight and second a broad exotherm around 400° with a further weight loss, presumably due to burning of organic matter. No evidence of melting is observed.

Fig. 1. DTA and TGA of Thorium (IV)-N-*m*-Tolyl-*m*-Nitrobenzohydroxamic Acid.

with aqueous solution of thorium(IV) to form the complex of type, II.

The thermogram recorded for thorium complex in flowing air shows no change in weight initially up

The major products of the chelate decomposition are found by UV, IR and X-ray to the thorium benzoate, benzanilide and finally metal oxide and tars. At about 220°-300° (First exotherm) the vaporisation of benzanilide with a gradual weight loss and about 300°-400° the decomposition of metal benzoate and formation of thorium oxide are expected (second exotherm). Thus the chemical and thermal analyses suggest that N-*m*-T-NBHA forms anhydrous stoichiometric precipitate with thorium and suitable as an analytical reagent for gravimetric estimation.

Thorium is precipitated quantitatively from a solution containing 5-15 mg. of thorium nitrate at

pH 4-4.5 with N-m-T-NBHA. The yellowish precipitate is weighed directly after drying at 110°-120°. The complex is fairly soluble in ethanol and chloroform but only sparingly soluble in ether, benzene, carbon tetrachloride acetone and glacial acetic acid. It is decomposed when treated with concentrated sulphuric, nitric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids. The analytical result indicate the composition of complex as $[C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_4]_4Th$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Professor A. B. Biswas, I.I.T., Bombay for his inspiring guidance. They are thankful to Dr. D. M. Chakravarti and Dr. S. Sampath, B.A.R.C., Bombay for thermal analysis of the samples and C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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